

EXPERIENCE OF DRILLING EXPLORATION WELLS IN DIFFICULT GEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AND MASTERING THEM BY THE METHOD OF DUAL COMPLETION OPERATION

Deryaev A.

*Candidate of Technical Sciences, Senior Researcher,
Scientific Research Institute of Natural Gas
of the State Concern „Turkmengas”,
Ashgabat, Turkmenistan
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Abstract

The article discusses the drilling of a prospecting and exploration well in difficult geological conditions. The design of the well and recommendations for drilling fluids are given, as well as the result obtained during the development of the method dual completion (DC) by two elevators with pumping and compressor pipes. When drilling this exploration well, the design was changed from the previously used conventional design for the Northern Goturdepe field. This work can be used for drilling deep wells in fields with complex mining and geological conditions and abnormally high reservoir pressure, in order to accelerate the development of multi-layer deposits.

Keywords: inhibited solution, collapse formation, tack, shank, water-based solution, blowout equipment, black clay.

When choosing and justifying the design of the North Goturdepe well № 37, the requirements of the "Safety Rules in the Oil and Gas Industry", the Regulations for calculating intermediate columns when Drilling wells in the oil and gas fields of the Western Part of Turkmenistan were taken into account and geological and technical information on previously drilled wells in the North Goturdepe field was used.

The choice of the well design was carried out in accordance with the intervals of compatibility of the well section according to the mining and geological drilling conditions, based on the forecast curves of reservoir pressure of rock rupture, and the following design was justified.

- the shaft direction Ø 720 mm descends to a depth of 10 m, is fixed with butobeton.

- the elongated direction of Ø530mm descends to a depth of 30 m, in order to overlap unstable, sandy-clay deposits and prevent erosion of the wellhead when drilling under the conductor. The height of the cement lifting is up to the wellhead.

The conductor Ø426mm descends to a depth of 594 m, provides overlap of the upper part of unstable sandy-clay quaternary deposits, isolation of the borehole from hydrostatically connected waters with the surface and installation of anti-blowout equipment.

The Ø324mm technical column descends to a depth of 2781 meters to overlap the swelling and collapse of the "black clays" of the Absheron tier and to shorten the interval of the open trunk when drilling for the second technical column Ø244.5 mm, was equipped with anti-blowout equipment and to ensure effective well management in case of possible manifestations. The descent of the Ø324mm technical column is carried out in two sections. The head of the I section is installed in a stable part of the open trunk section, in the range of 1700-2300 meters with logging adjustments. The height of the cement rise behind the column is up to the wellhead.

The descent of a technical column with a diameter of Ø244.5 mm is carried out to a depth of 4761 meters, in order to prevent the absorption of drilling mud with a density of 2.08g/cm³ and the seizure of drilling tools under the influence of pressure drop, as well as effective well management during manifestations using blowout equipment. The descent of the Ø244.5mm technical column is carried out in two sections, and the head of the I section was installed with a 50-100-meter approach into the Ø324mm technical column.

The descent of the operational filter shank Ø177.8mm is carried out to a depth of 4906 meters along the trunk (the length of the shank is 4691m-4906m), by installing a suspension device for 50-100 meters inside the casing Ø244.5 mm in order to overlap productive horizons [1].

The complex thermogeochemical conditions of drilling well №37 of the Northern Goturdepe field cause, from zero to the design depth, the need to use drilling fluids with a reduced water output and easily adjustable rheological and structural-mechanical parameters.

Water-based drilling fluids with an interval change of the type of chemical treatment, providing for a smooth transition from solutions stabilized with sodium - humates and lignosulfonates, are transferred to inhibited systems of alumocalcium solutions - ALKAR-3M

Temperature ranges of drilling fluids application:

- Oil-emulsion humate-lignosulfonate solution - +22 - +40 °C;

- Alumocalcium solutions - ALKAR-3M- +40-+121 °C.

Oil-emulsion humate-lignosulfonate solution is used from the beginning of drilling until its effectiveness drops. With a decrease in the effectiveness of the oil-emulsion humate-lignosulfonate solution, the transfer to the inhibited solutions of the ALKAR-3M system is carried out.

When drilling a well, starting from zero to a depth of 800 m, an oil-emulsion humate-lignosulfonate solution is used to drill unstable sand-clay rocks of the quaternary deposit and stabilize the wellbore.

Stabilizers reagents are used as regulators of the properties of the drilling mud: humates - coal-alkali reagent (KAR) and ligno-sulfonates - condensate of sulfate-alcohol bard (KSSB-2). Caustic soda (NaOH) is used to regulate the alkalinity of the calcium solubility solution in seawater. Oil and graphite are used from specialized reagents functionally designed to hydrophobize the solid phase of drilling mud and improve lubricating properties. To prevent foaming of the solution, a surface-active substance is used - surfactant HT-48. The hydrogen pH of the solution is 8.5-9.0 [2].

In the future, the processing of an oil-emulsion humate-lignosulfonate solution is carried out in order to reduce the viscosity of the solution and water loss to the

set values of the parameters. If the pH of the solution falls below the value, the required amount of NaOH should be introduced into the solution. Preparation and addition of reagents in the future is carried out as needed.

When drilling a well from a depth of 800 m to a depth of 2800 m, an inhibited ALKAR-3M solution is used. This solution is used to cover high-colloidal "black clays" of the Absheron tier, prone to collapses. ALKAR-3M suppresses the lyophilicity of clays, reduces the accumulation of excess volume of drilling mud and at the same time provides stability and strengthens the walls of the borehole.

Information on the recommended parameters of the drilling mud, when drilling for each column of the well №37 Northern Goturdepe are set out in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1.

Types and parameters of drilling fluids for drilling exploration well № 37 of the Northern Goturdepe field

Name (type) of the solution	Interval, m		Drilling mud parameters					
	From (top)	Up to (bottom)	Density, g/cm ³	Conditional viscosity, sec	Water output, cm ³ /30min	Crust, mm	Static shear stress, kgf/cm in, min	
							1	10
oil emulsion humate-lignosulfonate	0	800	1,26	40-60	10-12	2-3	10-20	20-30
ALKAR-3	800	1900	1,28	30-50	6-8	1-2	5-10	5-15
-II-	1900	2800	1,45	30-50	6-8	1-2	5-10	5-15
ALKAR-3M	2800	4000	1,35	30-50	3-4	0,5-1	5-10	5-15
-II-	4000	4300	1,40	30-50	3-4	0,5-1	5-10	5-15
-II-	4300	4600	1,45	30-50	3-4	0,5-1	5-10	5-15
-II-	4600	4800	1,64	30-50	3-4	0,5-1	5-15	5-20
ALKAR-3M	4800	4900	1,78	50-70	2-3	0,5	5-15	5-20
-II-	4900	5000	1,92	50-70	2-3	0,5	5-15	5-20
-II-	5000	5100	2,02	50-70	2-3	0,5	5-15	5-20
-II-	5100	5200	2,08	50-70	2-3	0,5	5-15	5-20

Reagents are used as regulators of drilling mud properties: stabilizers lignosulfonates - ferrochromolignosulfonate (FHLC) and KSSB-2, inhibitors - alkaline hydrolysates of Portland cement, thermostabilizers - sodium bichromates (Na₂Cr₂O₇) or potassium (K₂Cr₂O₇), alkalis - NaOH. The hydrogen pH of the solution is 10-12.

When drilling a well from a depth of 2800 m to a depth of 4800 m, an inhibited heat-resistant solution ALKAR-3M is used in the zone of elevated temperatures +113 ° C. This solution is used to suppress clays

of the lower red-colored thickness, stabilize the borehole and excessive saturation of the drilled rock. Provides stability of the solution parameters in the zone of elevated temperatures [3].

When drilling a well from a depth of 4800m to a depth of 5200m, an inhibited ALKAR-3M solution is used in the zone of elevated temperatures +121 ° C in order to suppress clays of the lower red-colored thickness and open productive layers of the well, stabilize the wellbore and excessive saturation of the drilled rock. Provides stability of the solution parameters in the zone of elevated temperatures.

Table 2.

Drilling mud parameters, when drilling an exploration well
№37 North Goturdepe field

Name (type) of the solution	Interval, m		Drilling mud parameters							
	From (top)	Up to (bottom)	Phase composition, % vol.			pH	Minera- lization, mg/l	Plastic viscosity, sDr	Dynamic shear stress, mg/cm ²	Ca+2 mg/l
			V _{oil}	V _{sol}	Y _f					
oil emulsion humate- lignosulfonate	0	800	8,62	77,46	13,92	8,5-9	13-15	15-18	30-33	300-400
ALKAR -3	800	1900	10,62	14,88	74,50	10-12	15-17	5-8	10-20	900-1500
-II-	1900	2800	10,62	20,60	68,78	10-12	15-17	10-12	10-20	900-1500
ALKAR-3M	2800	4000	13,21	17,24	69,55	10-12	15-17	10-12,	10-20	900-1500
-II-	4000	4300	13,21	20,15	66,64	10-12	15-17	10-12	10-20	900-1500
-II-	4300	4600	13,21	20,71	66,08	10-12	15-17	10-12	10-20	900-1500
	4600	4800	13,21	28,77	58,02	10-12	15-17	10-15	10-25	900-1500
ALKAR-3M	4800	4900	13,21	33,96	52,83	10-12	15-17	15-20	15-25	900-1500
-II-	4900	5000	13,21	40,35	46,44	10-12	15-17	15-25	15-30	900-1500
-II-	5000	5100	13,21	42,70	44,09	10-12	15-17	18-25	20-35	900-1500
-II-	5100	5200	13,21	47,65	39,14	10-12	15-17	20-30	25-40	900-1500

Drilling after the descent and fastening of the technical column Ø244.5 mm was carried out with a drill bit Ø215.9 mm using a rotary layout and drilling mud with a density of 1,80 g/cm³. At a depth of 4953 meters, drilling reached the design horizon and 12 productive horizons of the lower red color were opened. According to the research of logging data, a cement bridge was installed in the range of 4906-4953 m and a 177.8 mm shank was lowered to test objects in opened sections to a depth of 4906 m. With the 70m entrance of the upper end of the shank Ø177.8 mm into the inside of the

Ø244.5 mm technical column, the Weatherford shank suspension system was used to suspend and ensure the tightness of the upper end of the shank. The use of this system when the operational shank Ø177.8mm was lowered led to an increase in the reliability of the quality of cementing work and the tightness of the upper end.

The figure shows the design of well №37 on the Northern Goturdepe field with a two-lift tubing with downhole equipment for DC

Figure.

Design of well №37 with a two-lift tubing with downhole equipment for the DC at the North Goturdepe field

During the development of the well by the DC method, a large inflow of oil was obtained, the results of the studies are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Data on perforations and indications of studies during the development of well №37 of the Northern Goturdepe field

Object designation, type of perforator, number of holes	Distance of the test object, (m)	Age, artificial depth, (m)	Development results
I PKO -102 733	4448-4454 4612-4618 4626-4629	NK-7 NK-8	Oil inflow was recieved. $D_{\text{connect. pipe}} = 25\text{mm}$, $P_{\text{work}} = 35 \text{ atm}$. $Q_{\text{oil}} = 730,33 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$.

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